

SHORT COMMUNICATION

Terpenoids and Related Compounds—XV¹. Triterpenoids of the bark of *Rhododendron grande*

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The leaves of *Rhododendron grande* (Ericaceae) have been shown³ to contain campanulin, friedelin and ursolic acid besides quercetin and a neutral compound, m.p. 204–210°. The bark has been shown⁴ to contain a leucocyanidin dimer. The present communication reports the isolation of taraxeryl acetate, friedelin, taraxerol, β -sitosterol and betulinic acid from the bark of *R. grande*.

Dried and powdered bark of *R. grande* was extracted with benzene for 8 hrs. The extract was separated into a partially crystalline neutral fraction and a crystalline acidic fraction. The acidic fraction was esterified with diazomethane and the crude methyl ester chromatographed over a column of deactivated alumina. Elution with a mixture of pet. ether and benzene (3 : 2) afforded a crystalline solid which on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol furnished pure methyl betulinate, m.p. 220–225°, $[\alpha]_D + 3.8^\circ$ (Lit.⁵ m.p. 220–224°) identical with an authentic specimen. On acetylation it furnished methyl betulinate acetate, m.p. 198–200°, $[\alpha]_D + 14.3^\circ$ (Lit.⁵ m.p. 200–203°, $[\alpha]_D + 18^\circ$) identical (mixed m.p.) with an authentic specimen.

The neutral extract of the plant was chromatographed over a column of activated alumina. After a forerun of waxy material, elution with a mixture of pet. ether and benzene (3 : 2) furnished a crystalline solid, which after crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol yielded taraxeryl acetate, m.p. 290–294°, $[\alpha]_D + 5.6^\circ$ (Lit.⁶ m.p. 298–305°, $[\alpha]_D + 9.5^\circ$) identical (mixed m.p.) with an authentic specimen.

Elution of the column with benzene yielded a crystalline solid, which is crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol gave friedelin, m.p. 250–256°, $[\alpha]_D + 27.4^\circ$, (Lit.⁷ m.p. 254–256°, $[\alpha]_D + 25^\circ$), identical (mixed m.p.) with an authentic specimen.

1. Part XIV. P. Sengupta, J. Mukherjee and Ashesh K. Dey, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, communicated.
2. Present address : Department of Chemistry, Arizona State University, Tempe, Arizona, U.S.A.
3. S. Rangaswami and P. Venkateswarlu, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1965, **62A**, 224.
4. S. Rangaswami and P. Venkateswarlu, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1966, **64A**, 185.
5. P. Boiteau, B. Paisch and A. Rakoto Ratsimamanga. *Les Triterpenoides en physiologie vegetale et animale*, Gauthier-Villars, Paris, 1964, 116.
6. Ref. 5, p. 168.
7. Ref. 5, p. 174.

Elution of the column with ether gave a solid, m.p. 272–274°, that was identified as taraxerol by conversion into its acetate, m.p. 291–295°, identical (mixed m.p.) with an authentic specimen of taraxeryl acetate.

Further elution of the column with a mixture of ether and chloroform (1 : 1) yielded a solid, m.p. 133–138°, $[\alpha]_D - 40^\circ$, which was identified as β -sitosterol by conversion into its acetate m.p. 120–123° and its benzoate, m.p. 146–149° $[\alpha]_D - 10^\circ$, that were identical with the respective authentic specimens.

All the compounds reported gave correct C, H—analytical data.

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